

Comparative Analysis of Pectinase Activity in Soil borne Fungal Pathogens of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Pectinases are crucial extracellular enzymes involved in plant cell wall degradation and play a significant role in the pathogenicity of soil-borne fungi. The present study evaluates the pectinase activity of seven major fungal pathogens associated with groundnut using pectin as a substrate under substrate and non-substrate conditions. The results revealed that *Rhizoctonia solani* exhibited the highest pectinase activity (80% in substrate and 62% in non-substrate medium), followed by *Fusarium solani* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Lower activity was observed in *Aspergillus flavus*. The study highlights the enzymatic variability among pathogens and their potential role in disease severity. These findings contribute to understanding fungal virulence and may aid in developing eco-friendly disease management strategies.

Keywords: Pectinase, Groundnut, Enzyme activity, Pathogenicity

INTRODUCTION

Pectin is a complex structural heteropolysaccharide predominantly present in the primary cell wall and middle lamella of higher plants, where it plays a crucial role in maintaining cell adhesion and structural integrity. The degradation of pectin is mediated by a group of enzymes collectively known as pectinases or pectinolytic enzymes, which catalyze the breakdown of pectic substances into simpler molecules (Kashyap *et al.*, 2001; Jayani *et al.*, 2005). These enzymes are widely distributed in nature and are produced by a variety of microorganisms, particularly fungi, bacteria, and yeasts (Pedrolli *et al.*, 2009).

Among microorganisms, fungi are considered the most efficient producers of pectinases due to their ability to secrete large quantities of extracellular enzymes. Fungal pectinases have been extensively studied for their role in industrial applications as well as in plant pathology (Whitaker, 1990; Sethi *et al.*, 2016). In phytopathogenic fungi, pectinases act as key virulence factors by degrading the middle lamella of plant tissues, thereby facilitating host tissue maceration and colonization (Atta and Ruiz-Larrea, 2022). This enzymatic degradation weakens plant defense barriers and enhances the invasion process, leading to disease development. Several fungal genera such as

Aspergillus, *Fusarium*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Macrophomina*, and *Sclerotium* are well-known for their pectinolytic capabilities and are commonly associated with soilborne plant diseases (Silva et al., 2003; KC et al., 2020). These fungi exhibit variability in enzyme production depending on environmental conditions and substrate availability. Studies have shown that the presence of pectin in the growth medium significantly induces pectinase production, indicating its role as an effective substrate and inducer (Mulluye et al., 2021; Awe et al., 2023).

Screening and characterization studies of soil fungi have revealed that a substantial proportion of isolates possess strong pectinolytic activity, which is directly correlated with their pathogenic potential (Dey et al., 2023; Dwivedi et al., 2023). Higher enzyme activity is often associated with increased virulence, as it enhances the ability of pathogens to degrade host cell walls and establish infection. Therefore, understanding the enzymatic profile of fungal pathogens is essential for elucidating mechanisms of plant disease progression.

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is one of the most important oilseed crops cultivated worldwide, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. However, its productivity is severely affected by various soilborne fungal pathogens that cause diseases such as root rot, stem rot, and collar rot. These pathogens, including *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Fusarium solani*, and *Sclerotium rolfsii*, are known to produce cell wall degrading enzymes, especially pectinases, which play a central role in host tissue invasion and disease establishment (Sethi et al., 2016; KC et al., 2020).

The enzymatic degradation of plant tissues through pectinase production is therefore considered a major mechanism of pathogenicity in soil-borne fungi. Comparative evaluation of pectinase activity among different fungal pathogens provides valuable insights into their virulence potential and ecological adaptability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Seven soil-borne fungal pathogens were used in the study, including *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium solani*, *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Pythium myriotylum*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, and *Sclerotium rolfsii*,

representing a range of plant pathogenic fungi with varying enzymatic activity.

The experiment was conducted to assess pectinase activity using two types of media i.e. substrate medium containing pectin as the carbon source and non-substrate medium lacking pectin.

Enzyme activity was measured by the viscosity reduction method. The efflux time of the mixture at 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 minutes was recorded with the help of stop watch. The percent loss of viscosity was calculated by using following formula-

$$\text{Percent loss of viscosity} = \frac{T_0 - T_x}{T_0 - T_w} \times 100$$

Where,

T₀ = Flow time in seconds at zero time

T_x = Flow time of the reaction mixture at time T

T_w = Flow time of distilled water

Composition of Media for Pectin Production (pH - 5)

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Gm/lit
1	Pectinase	10 gm
2	KNO ₃	2.5 gm.
3	KH ₂ PO ₄	1.0 gm.
4	Mgso ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.5 gm
5	Distilled water	1000 ml

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pectinase Activity:

The results (Table & Graph) clearly indicate variation in enzyme production among fungal pathogens.

Table: Pectinase Activity of Soil borne Fungal Pathogens of Groundnut

Sr. No.	Fungal Pathogens	Substrate (%)	Non-substrate (%)
1	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	30	20
2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	58	36
3	<i>Fusarium solani</i>	78	40
4	<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>	69	52
5	<i>Pythium myriotylum</i>	63	39
6	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	80	62
7	<i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>	76	59

Graph: Pectinase Activity of Soil-borne Fungal Pathogens of *Arachis hypogaea* L.

The results indicate that *Rhizoctonia solani* exhibited the highest enzymatic activity, with 80% activity in substrate conditions and 62% in non-substrate conditions. This clearly reflects its strong enzymatic machinery, which plays a crucial role in host tissue degradation and nutrient acquisition. Such elevated enzyme production is often directly associated with increased pathogenic potential, suggesting that *R. solani* is highly virulent and capable of causing severe plant diseases under favorable conditions. A group of fungi showed moderate enzymatic activity, including *Fusarium solani* (78%, 40%), *Sclerotium rolfsii* (76%, 59%), and *Macrophomina phaseolina* (69%, 52%). These organisms are well-documented aggressive plant pathogens, and their relatively high enzyme production supports their ability to infect and colonize host tissues effectively. Although slightly lower than *R. solani*, their enzymatic levels are sufficient to facilitate host invasion, indicating significant pathogenic potential and adaptability in different environmental conditions.

In contrast, *Pythium myriotylum* (63%, 39%), *Aspergillus niger* (58%, 36%), and *Aspergillus flavus* (30%, 20%) demonstrated comparatively lower enzymatic activity. This reduced enzyme production suggests a lower degree of virulence and limited capacity for host tissue degradation. While these fungi may still act as pathogens or opportunistic organisms, their overall infectivity appears less aggressive compared to the highly active and moderately active groups.

Effect of Substrate

All fungi showed higher pectinase activity in substrate medium, confirming that pectin acts as an inducer for

enzyme production. Similar induction effects have been reported in *Aspergillus niger* cultures.

Role in Pathogenicity

Pectinase enzymes degrade plant tissues, enabling pathogen invasion. Fungi producing higher pectinase levels exhibit increased disease severity. This supports earlier findings that fungal pectinases are major virulence factors in plant diseases.

- Clear dominance of *Rhizoctonia solani*
- Significant difference between substrate and non-substrate conditions
- Correlation between enzyme activity and pathogenic potential.

The observed variation in enzymatic activity among the studied fungi strongly correlates with their pathogenic potential, as higher production of cell wall-degrading enzymes is a key factor in host invasion and tissue colonization. The highest activity recorded in *Rhizoctonia solani* supports its well-documented status as a highly aggressive pathogen capable of efficient host degradation (Kubicek *et al.*, 2014; Dean *et al.*, 2012).

Similarly, moderate enzymatic activity in *Fusarium solani*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, and *Macrophomina phaseolina* aligns with their recognized ability to cause significant plant diseases through enzymatic breakdown of plant tissues (Punja, 2005; Sharma & Ghosh, 2016). In contrast, the comparatively lower enzyme production observed in *Pythium myriotylum*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Aspergillus flavus* indicates reduced virulence, although these organisms may still act as opportunistic pathogens under favorable conditions (Amaike & Keller, 2011). Overall, these findings are consistent with previous studies

emphasizing the central role of extracellular enzymes in determining the infectivity and aggressiveness of phytopathogenic fungi (Agrios, 2008; Islam *et al.*, 2012).

CONCLUSION

The present study clearly demonstrates that *Rhizoctonia solani* is the most potent producer of pectinase among the tested soil-borne fungal pathogens of groundnut. The results further indicate that the presence of substrate (pectin) significantly enhances enzyme production, confirming its role as an inducer. A positive correlation was observed between higher pectinase activity and increased pathogenicity, suggesting that fungi with greater enzymatic capability possess stronger infection potential. These findings provide valuable insights into fungal virulence mechanisms and can be effectively utilized in developing sustainable disease management strategies, including biological control approaches and the selection or development of resistant crop varieties.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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